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Measurement-Based Global Ocean Current Energy Resource Assessment

Mahsan Sadoughipour ^{a,1}, James VanZwieten ^a, Yufei Tang ^a, Lucas Almeida ^b

^aFlorida Atlantic University, 777 Glades Rd., Boca Raton, FL, 33004, USA

^bPine Crest School, 1501 NE 62nd Street, Fort Lauderdale, FL, 33334, USA

Abstract

Global electricity demand is increasing every day due to developing economies in different parts of the world and population growth. Considering the need to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, renewable energy plays an essential role in meeting the demand for this increased power production. To help meet this need, electricity can be produced from open ocean currents such as the Gulf Stream, Kuroshio, and Agulhas currents. This ocean current based electricity production can provide predictable and nearly continuous electricity generation along the western boundaries of ocean basins. This resource has been assessed globally using numerical model data and regionally using measurements. Still, a global measurement-based ocean current energy assessment has not previously been made available to the ocean current energy community. Therefore, this paper presents a global measurement-based assessment of ocean current energy created using twenty years of drifter data.

Keywords: Ocean Current; Power Density; Resource Assessment

1. Introduction

Global electricity consumption has been continuously increasing in recent decades, with an average annual growth rate of 2.4% over the last five years [1]. Fossil fuels are currently the dominant source of electricity generation. Therefore, increasing the share of renewable energy resources for power generation is crucial to reduce reliance on fossil fuels and consequently reduce greenhouse gas emissions in this sector [2]. The oceans, which cover more than 70% of the earth, can provide tremendous amounts of renewable energy in both kinetic (i.e., ocean current, ocean wave, tidal range, tidal current) and potential (i.e., ocean thermal, salinity gradient) forms. Marine renewable energy is a promising source of clean energy, especially for coastal areas and islands.

In addition to technological advancement, assessment and mapping of ocean energy resources are crucial measures for the market deployment of ocean energy. Assessing ocean resources in each form involves identifying potential areas, measuring the average energy resource, and describing it through parameters [3]. Numerous studies have been carried out to estimate the different types of available ocean energy. The estimated theoretical power that can be harnessed from the wave power resource of the planet is approximately 2.11 ± 0.05 TW with a 95% confidence level, and it is almost evenly distributed between the northern and southern hemispheres [4]. The maximum steady-state electrical output generated by Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion (OTEC) is estimated to be approximately 3 TW [5].

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: msadoughipou2023@fau.edu

Ocean currents refer to the continuous movement of seawater within ocean gyres, and a considerable amount of kinetic energy is available near the surface of oceans due to these currents. Accurate assessments and detailed characterizations of the available ocean current resources are essential for effectively planning and developing ocean current energy converters. Several studies focus on estimating the regional or global available ocean current energy based on numerical models. In [6], data generated by the HYCOM (Hybrid Coordinate Ocean Model) over a period of three years were used to assess the kinetic energy flux (KEF) observed in ocean current systems globally, with the most energy-dense ocean currents found in the Gulf Stream current off Florida's east coast. The estimated average power available throughout Florida's current share of the Gulf Stream is around 5.1 GW [7], with practical power extraction around 2 GW [8]. The estimated mean power in this current increases to 18.6 GW if the entire share of the U.S. East Coast from Florida to North Carolina of the Gulf Stream be observed [7]. In another study, the annual and seasonal average current speed and kinetic energy flux along the Brazilian coast is estimated over a 10-year period [9]. In [10], the potential power density of the East Coast of the U.S. was evaluated solely based on measurement data.

This study aims to comprehensively analyze the global ocean current resource based solely on measurement data. Drifter data, collected by the World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE), are used to calculate and map surface current's average kinetic energy flux. Furthermore, a more detailed analysis is conducted in regions with higher power density, including depth contours used to investigate the total water depth where this resource exists. Another critical factor assessed in this study is the distance between the areas with the most energy-dense ocean currents and the nearest landmass.

2. Resource assessment methodology

Twenty years of drifter data, which are publicly available, are used as an input. These data, collected by the World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE), include latitude, longitude, and near-surface current velocity [11]. First, missed and error values are found and eliminated from the dataset. Then, latitude and longitude data are used to define a rectangular grid with fixed increments of latitude and longitude as the basis for averaging the data. The availability of enough data in each grid and accuracy are the two factors considered for determining the fixed step of latitude and longitude. Next, the kinetic energy flux is calculated for each section according to:

$$P_{avg} = \frac{1}{2N} \rho_{sw} \sum_{i=1}^N v_i^3 \quad (1)$$

where P_{avg} is the mean power density in the grid block, ρ_{sw} is the density of seawater, which is estimated as $1,030 \text{ kg/m}^3$, v_i is the current speed for datapoint i within the block of interest, and N is the number of datapoints within a block. For the sections that no data points are available, the value of P_{avg} is considered zero.

For this paper, the rectangular grid is $0.2^\circ \times 0.2^\circ$, which is approximately equivalent to a square with the length of each side of 22.2 km at the equator, but with the longitudinal distance decreasing toward the poles. To assess the accuracy of P_{avg} for the specified block size, the confidence interval at 95% confidence level is calculated using equations (2) and (3), with a focus on regions with high power density (more than 500 W/m^2). We are only interested in high power density areas since they are potential sites for further studies and ocean current turbine installation.

$$MOE_\gamma = z_\gamma \times \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} \quad (2)$$

$$CI = P_{avg} \pm MOE_\gamma \quad (3)$$

where MOE_γ is margin of error, γ is confidence coefficient (set at 0.95 in this assessment), z_γ is the z-score at a given γ which is derived from z-score table, σ is standard deviation and N is the number of available data in each grid. In equation (3) CI is the confidence interval.

After calculating the power density for all the grid blocks, the map of power density for the world is created (Fig.1). For better data visualization, land and regions without data are shaded green. Furthermore, bathymetric data are used to determine the water depth in different locations. This map clearly highlights the energy-dense ocean currents which run along the western boundaries of the ocean basins, which exceed 1000 W/m^2 in many areas. The highest power density can be found near the Southeast coast of the U.S. (Florida to North Carolina), East and Southeast coasts of Africa (Somalia, Kenya, Tanzania, and South Africa), and East of Asia (Japan and Philippines). These areas have

locations with a measured power density greater than $2 \text{ kW}/\text{m}^2$. In addition, slightly lower power density can be seen off northern South America (Brazil and French Guiana), Vietnam, and the east coast of Australia in the Pacific Ocean.

Fig. 1. Average power density calculated using drifter data in W/m^2 .

3. Results

Fig. 2 to Fig. 5 show zoomed in views of the KEF (left figures) for the three regions that have KEF more than $2000W/m^2$, as well as off northern Brazil/French Guiana. For each area, the ratio of margin of error (Eq. 3) to average power density (Eq. 1) in different blocks is also provided (right figures) to help quantify the accuracy of calculated KEF for these regions. The white line in the figures on the left provides the depth contour of 300 m.

Fig. 2. Calculated average power density off SE North America (Florida to North Carolina), and the corresponding normalized margin of error.

As seen in Fig. 2, ocean currents with energy densities more than $1500 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$ approximately follow the 300 m depth contour off the southeast US from approximately Miami, FL to around Cape Hatteras, NC, where the high energy density currents rapidly move to much deeper water with increasing latitude. Energy densities above $1500W/m^2$ can be found within the 300 m depth contour from about 25° N to 32° N , whereas they are typically slightly outside this depth contour from 32° N to 36° N . Off the east coast of Florida, the most energy-dense currents (greater than $2000 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$) are in total water depths between 300 m and 600 m. However, as we move to the north and North Carolina's currents, the depth of ocean for power densities greater than $2 \text{ kW}/\text{m}^2$ is more than 900 m. Power densities greater than $2.5 \text{ kW}/\text{m}^2$ can be found between latitudes of 26° N to 30° N , as well as between 35.5° N to 36.5° N . The highest power densities (near $3 \text{ kW}/\text{m}^2$) can be found at $28.5^\circ \text{ N}, 79.9^\circ \text{ W}$, and $29.3^\circ \text{ N}, 79.9^\circ \text{ W}$ which are approximately 30 km and 100 km away from the shore, respectively. The 95% confidence intervals for these results are shown in Fig. 2-Right, indicating that this confidence interval is primarily between 8-15% of the calculated energy densities where the energy densities exceed $500 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$.

Fig. 3 shows the KEF off the northern coast of Brazil and French Guiana. This indicates that energy densities around $1000\text{--}1500\text{ W/m}^2$ exist slightly north of the 300 m depth contour from latitudes of about -3°N to 7°N . Off Brazil, the water depth rapidly increases outside of the 300 m depth contour with most of the energy densities greater than 1500 W/m^2 is found where the water depth exceeds 900 m. However, energy densities more than 1500 W/m^2 are seen close to the shore and in shallower waters from $5^\circ\text{N}, 55^\circ\text{W}$ to $8^\circ\text{N}, 50^\circ\text{W}$. Unfortunately, the uncertainty in the power calculations for this area is relatively high (20-90% of the mean value) and therefore additional measurements are needed to quantify better the potential of this relatively shallow water resource that is close to shore.

Fig. 3. Calculated average power density in Brazil and French Guiana, and the corresponding normalized margin of error.

Fig. 4 indicates that high power density areas (more than 2.5 kW/m^2) exist within 30 km to 70 km distance from the coastline off South Africa. Power densities around 1.5 kW/m^2 can be found within 300 m depth contour from about -35°N to -31°N , but the depth of ocean where the power density is more than 2.5 kW/m^2 is between 700 m and 1000 m. The 95% confidence interval for these results (Fig. 4-Right) indicates that this confidence interval is primarily between 10-20% of the mean values, with a few blocks located closer to shore having greater uncertainties of around 40%.

Fig. 4. Calculated average power density in South Africa and the corresponding normalized margin of error.

The power density of ocean currents near Japan is shown in Fig. 5. The power density in this area primarily ranges between 1 kW/m^2 to 1.5 kW/m^2 with very limited areas that have power around 2 kW/m^2 . The depth contour suggests that no ocean current resource more than 500 W/m^2 can be found in depths less than 300 m. In addition, the highest power density exists as far as 120 km from the shore, but areas with 1.5 kW/m^2 power density can be found less than 30 km from the shore. It is noted that the relatively large spatial averaging ($\sim 22\text{ km} \times 22\text{ km}$) necessary for driving down the block averages' uncertainty is inadequate for capturing smaller scale energy intensifications that can result from local bathymetric features. The 95% uncertainty range associated with the power calculations for this area is primarily between 10-20% of the calculated energy densities.

Fig. 5. Calculated average power density in Japan and Taiwan, and the corresponding normalized margin of error.

4. Conclusion

In this study, we use drifter data to assess the global ocean current resources, with the uncertainty range associated with a confidence level of 95% provided for energy-dense areas. Energy densities above 1500 W/m^2 were common in the waters off Florida's east coast and South Africa in water depth around 300 m, but not in other regions. The results for North America and Japan showed smaller uncertainty values (typically 10% of calculated energy densities), while larger uncertainty ranges were typically found off South Africa and South America (typically 25%), especially for the relatively shallow water area that showed energy densities of around 1000 W/m^2 off northern Brazil and French Guiana. It is important to note that the relatively large spatial averaging ($\sim 22 \text{ km} \times 22 \text{ km}$) necessary for driving down the uncertainty in the block averages is not adequate for capturing smaller scale energy intensifications that can result from local bathymetric features common in near-shore regions and that other methods may be necessary for evaluating these areas. Future work includes comparing these measurements with ADCP measurements available in high energy areas.

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References

- [1] International Energy Agency, World Energy Outlook 2022, IEA; 2022.
- [2] Jenniches S. Assessing the regional economic impacts of renewable energy sources—A literature review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*; 2018; 93:35-51.
- [3] Uihlein A, Magagna D. Wave and tidal current energy—A review of the current state of research beyond technology. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*; 2016; 58:1070-81.
- [4] Gunn K, Stock-Williams C. Quantifying the global wave power resource. *Renewable energy*; 2012; 44:296-304.
- [5] Nihous GC. A preliminary assessment of ocean thermal energy conversion resources. *Journal of Energy Resource Technology*; 2007; 129: 10–17.
- [6] VanZwieten JH, Duerr AE, Alsenas GM, Hanson HP. Global Ocean current energy assessment: an initial look. In *Proceedings of the 1st Marine Energy Technology Symposium (METS13) hosted by the 6th annual Global Marine Renewable Energy Conference*; 2013; pp. 10-11.
- [7] Haas K. Assessment of energy production potential from ocean currents along the United States coastline. *Georgia Institute of Technology*. Atlanta, GA (United States); 2013.
- [8] Board OS, National Research Council, Marine and Hydrokinetic Energy Technology Assessment Committee. An evaluation of the US Department of Energy's marine and hydrokinetic resource assessments. *National Academies Press*; 2013.
- [9] Shadman M, Silva C, Faller D, Wu Z, de Freitas Assad LP, Landau L, Levi C, Estefen SF. Ocean renewable energy potential, technology, and deployments: a case study of Brazil. *Energies*; 2019;12(19):36-58.
- [10] Machado MC, VanZwieten JH, Callou AP, Pinos I. A measurement-based analyses of the hydrokinetic energy in the Gulf Stream. In *ISOPE International Ocean and Polar Engineering Conference*; 2015.
- [11] Elipot, S., R. Lumpkin, R. C. Perez, J. M. Lilly, J. J. Early, and A. M. Sykulski (2016), A global surface drifter dataset at hourly resolution, *J. Geophys. Res. Oceans*, 121, doi:10.1002/2016JC011716.